

Acceptorless Dehydrogenative Condensation: Synthesis of Indoles and Quinolines from Diols and Anilines.

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Abstract: The use of diols and anilines as reagents for the preparation of indoles represents a challenge in organic synthesis. By means of acceptorless dehydrogenative condensation heterocycles, such as indoles, can be obtained. Herein we present an experimental and theoretical study for this purpose employing heterogeneous catalysts Pt/Al₂O₃ and ZnO in combination with acid catalyst (*p*-TSA) and NMP as solvent. Under our optimized conditions, diols excess have been reduced down to 2 equivalents. This represents a major advance, and allows the use of other diols. 2,3-Butanediol or 1,2-cyclohexanediol have been employed affording 2,3-dimethyl indoles and tetrahydrocarbazoles. In addition, 1,3-propanediol has been employed to prepare quinolines or natural and synthetic Julolidines.

Introduction

Borrowing Hydrogen reactions (BH)¹, also known as Hydrogen Autotransfer reactions (HA)², have gained significant attention in the last decade. This type of reactions falls within the framework of green chemistry;³ both for its high atomic efficiency and for the use of catalysis. In addition, only water is obtained as side-product. BH process is based on an alcohol dehydrogenation followed by imine formation as shown in Scheme 1 (a). The hydrogen abstracted from the alcohols is then employed to form the secondary amine by rehydrogenation.²⁻⁵ Within all contributions reported on this reaction, homogeneous catalysts are by far the most used.² These types of reactions are applied to many alcohols, but diols are particularly interesting. Diols can lead to simple and/or double HA/BH reactions as reported by Williams⁴ or even frustrated-HA/BH reactions (also named as acceptorless dehydrogenative condensation (ADH), Scheme 1),⁶ ADH may yield to heterocycles such as pyrroles.⁷ Interestingly, ethylene glycol has not been extensively employed compared to other diols. However, ethylene glycol can be used to prepare amino-alcohols⁸ and, more importantly, indoles⁹ (Scheme 1 middle). Madsen and collaborators published that other type of 1,2-diols can be used for indole synthesis. In their work, homogeneous ruthenium or iridium catalysts were employed with equimolecular aniline/diol amounts.¹⁰ Heterogeneous catalyst for HA/BH or ADH have been less exploited.¹¹ As a general trend, an excess of alcohol is necessary for efficient ADH reactions.³ In our previous studies, ethylene glycol was indeed used also as a

solvent.^{8,9} When the alcohol is accessible (economically) and excess may be acceptable; as it's the situation with ethanol, methanol, benzyl alcohol or ethylene glycol. When more complex alcohols are required, the excess outstands as a major drawback for the methodology. However, complex diols do work on these systems. As it can be concluded regarding pioneering works from Watanabe,¹² where **even 1,2-cyclohexanediol** was employed for the preparation of tetrahydrocarbazoles. Herein we focus on optimizing the conditions for the formation of complex indoles through heterogeneous catalysis. **Theoretical calculations have been carried out in order to establish a plausible reaction mechanism.**

Scheme 1. a) General ADH reaction mechanism. b) Previous results with ethylene glycol and anilines, c) **Optimal conditions with two equivalents of diol.**

Results and Discussion

In our previous studies we found that a combination of Pt/Al₂O₃ and ZnO was able to activate ethylene glycol.⁹ Under these conditions, hydrogen was *in situ* released. Glycoaldehyde production in the presence of anilines at high temperature triggered the indole formation cycle. The practical use of other 1,2-diols is not only based on price, but also on their physical state (many of them are solid compounds and can not act as solvent). Thus, an BH/HA compatible solvent was required.

Figure 1. Solvent screening and *p*-TSA results.

Reaction optimization:

Trimethoxy aniline **1a** was chosen as model aniline due to its performance on ADH reaction observed in our previous work.⁹ With this compound different solvents were evaluated. NMP afforded the best results, imino ketone **2a** (37%) and a 37% of indole **3a** were obtained. DMA, DMF and DMSO did not improve those results. Using diglyme, low yields were also obtained. The presence of **2a** was unexpected. In any of our previous results with ethylene glycol (as solvent) ketones or aldehydes were never observed; in contrast, morpholines, diamines or amino alcohols were common side products,^{8,9} but not imino ketones. Indeed, by employing o 2,4-dimethylaniline (**1b**) amino ketones **2b** were obtained, no trace of the corresponding indole was observed. *p*-TSA was introduced in the reaction expecting that this acid catalysis will help the intramolecular cyclization. To note, in the literature compound **2a** was directly obtained by condensation of the 3-hydroxybutan-2-one and **1a**.¹² A major difference with secondary alcohols under BH/HA cycles is that ketones are obtained instead of aldehydes (glycolaldehyde for ethylene glycol). Ketones appear to be less reactive towards the S_EAr reactions compared to aldehydes. Acids (both Lewis and Brønsted) are common catalysts for these reactions. When *p*-TSA was introduced in the reaction (5%) yields raised 99 % for compound **3a**. With this new catalysts combination, solvents were screened again with a significant improvement of yields. NMP remained as the most efficient (Figure 1, bottom). In addition, equivalent amount could be reduced down to 2 equivalents keeping concentration at 0.8 M and reaction time in no longer than 48 h (controlled by TLC).

2,3-Butanediol.

In Figure 2 aniline scope with 2,3-butanediol is presented. Substituted anilines **1a-c** afforded indoles **3a-c** with good yields except for compound **3c** (30%). However, no trace of amino ketone was observed. 1-Naphtyl amine (**1d**) afforded indole **3d** in 79% and aniline compound **3e** in a 70%. 2,5-dimethoxyaniline gave indole **3f** in 99%. Tetrahydroquinoline allowed the synthesis of tricyclic compound **3g** in excellent yield of 86%. However, indoline did not afford indole formation. Instead, amino ketone **2d** was isolated in 80%. Structures with [5,5,6] condensed cycles are not commonly reported in the literature due to ring tension. The presence of amino ketone clearly points towards this explanation. 1,2-Diamino benzene afforded quinoxaline **4** (88%). The presence of compound **4** can also be related to the imino ketone intermediate (*vide infra*).

Figure 2. Aniline scope with 2,3-butanediol.

Mechanism studies and theoretical calculations.

To shed light on the mechanism and understand the observed differences (the presence of amino ketones and the requirement of acid catalysis) DFT calculations (B3LYP-D3) and additional experiments were performed. It is important to note that this process starts with a single alcohol dehydrogenation and, after this step, an imine formation.

Scheme 2 shows the control reactions with 2,3-butanediol and ethylene glycol. **Employing two equivalents of ethylene glycol (Pt/Al₂O₃ NMP, without acid catalyst) compound 5 was obtained in 50% yield and 75% when *p*-TSA was used.** This difference in performance is remarkable, because if ethylene glycol, is used as solvent (6 mL) **5 can be obtained in 88% yield according**

to our previous studies.⁹ Zhang and collaborators also observed this difference in their approach with Ru-Xanthphos catalyst.¹⁴ In fact, under their conditions, ethylene glycol was not able to undergo indole formation with aniline. Consequently, dehydrogenation of ethylene glycol is more difficult to achieve compared to 2,3-butanediol. In Watanabe original studies a similar behavior as reported,¹² higher yields with 2,3-butanediol were obtained. However, the most surprising result of these reactions was the absence of aldehydes in the reaction medium. Without acid catalysis amino ketones appear (Scheme 2 top); in the case of ethylene glycol, aldehydes have never been observed, either in these conditions or in our previous studies. In addition, glycolaldehyde or 3-hydroxybutan-2-one (dehydrogenation products, scheme 2 bottom) are not observed in reaction mixtures, this is in coherence with a fast initial imine formation. Figure 3 presents the overall mechanism proposal for this reaction.

Scheme 2. Ethylene glycol *versus* 2,3-butanediol. (N.O. = not observed)

As it can be seen in figure 3 (see also Table S4), starting from the imine (**1a**), an initial tautomeric equilibrium yields towards the imino ketone. This equilibrium is mediated by a water molecule that acts as catalyst being present in **TS1a** and **TS2a** with 41.2 and 34.8 kcal/mol barriers respectively. The overall energetic balance affords final ketone as more stable than any of the intermediates. Water is present as side product from the imine formation and also because ZnO is used as water suspension.

Figure 3. Mechanism for the transformation of the imine **Ia** into indole **II** catalysed with H₂O at B3LYP-D3 level.

These calculations agree with the experimental observations as only amino ketones are observed. Intramolecular cyclisation is the following step. As it can be noted, a prochiral carbon is present in ketone **IN2a**. Thus two different attacks can take place, *re* (figure 3 mid, red path) or *si* (blue path) attacks (both mediated by a water molecule again) have similar TS energies (**TS3a1** and **TS3a2**: 36.9 and 37.5 kcal/mol). Final products **IN3a1** and **IN3a2** are diastereoisomers (being both racemic due to the initial racemic state of 3-hydroxybutan-2-one). At this stage water elimination is required to create aromaticity in the 5-membered ring. However, only *syn*-elimination is possible, being catalyzed by water molecule in a cyclic **TS4a1**. *Anti*-elimination cannot happen, under an accessible energy level, due to the trans arrangement of alcohol and hydrogen group, even with a water molecule. For a more general comparison,

similar calculations were performed with ethylene glycol, (See SI, Figures S15-S17 at B3LYP level).

Two significant differences can be found. First, transition state for the intramolecular cyclization is lower, 3.4 kcal/mol, this is in coherence with the experimental observation: the absence of aldehydes and the spontaneous conversion to indoles upon oxidation.^{8,9} The second relevant difference is the absence of *re* and *si* faces, as a consequence and hydrogen atom (of the CH₂) is always accessible to eliminate a water molecule.

Next, the system was modeled with acid catalysis (Figure 4). Indeed, major changes are present under these situations. First, tautomeric equilibrium is affected, reducing TS barriers significantly (Ts1b).

Figure 4. Mechanism for the transformation of the imine Ia into indole II catalysed with H₂O and *p*-TSA at B3LYP-D3 level.

Under the acidic conditions of *p*-TSA (pKa = -2.8) the imine **1a** is initially protonated providing **1b** (Figure 4). The positive charge is delocalized between the N and the C of the imine (in fact between the H on the N and the C-2 of the imine see figure S3). The mechanism by which **1b** is transformed in indole **II** differs dramatically from the one described above without catalysis. Isomerization of protonated imine **1b** in the ketone **IN2b1** takes place in a single stage (to note, without acid catalysis requires two stages; **TS1a-TS2a** Figure 3), through the **TS1b** with an energy barrier (ΔG) of 25.5 kcal / mol. In **TS1b**, transposition of H over C-1 to C-2 occurs through a three-member cyclic state. This transposition is favored by the positive partial charge on C-2 (see SI). The H₂O acts by stabilizing the TS by forming two hydrogen bonds with the protons over the N and O of the hydroxyl.

The nucleophilic attack of the aromatic ring to the carbonyl of the ketone **IN2b1** is preceded by the initial transfer of the proton the carbonyl to give **IN2b2**. The presence of the H₂O molecule facilitates the transfer of hydrogen atom. This enhances the electrophilic character and facilitates the attack of the aromatic ring, being indeed a classic acid catalyzed S_EAr.

In this case, again the intramolecular S_EAr can proceed through *re*-attack and *si*-attack on both sides of the ketone carbonyl. The *re*-attack gives rise to the **IN3b1** through the

TS3b1, with an energy barrier from the **IN2b1** of 35.1 kcal / mol (blue path). Similarly, the **si**-attack (red path) leads to **IN3b2** through **TS3b2** ($\Delta G = 35.2$ kcal / mol from **IN2b1**). In both intermediates **IN3b1** / **IN3b2** there has been no abstraction of H over the ring and therefore its rearomatization. This situation differs from that observed for the corresponding **IN3a1** / **IN3a2**, of the mechanism without acid catalysis, where the simultaneous rearomatization of the benzene ring occurs.

Both cationic alcohols **IN3b1** / **IN3b2** evolve through **TS4b1** / **TS4b2** to the same **IN4b** carbocation. In **TS4b1** / **TS4b2** the abstraction of the H occurs with rearomatization of the benzene ring and the simultaneous expulsion of the hydroxyl. In this case there is no geometric restriction observed for the case of **TS4a1** / **TS4a2** (without acid catalysis, figure 3), and both the path through **re**-attack and **si**-attack can lead to the final product. The energy barriers from **IN3b1** / **IN3b2** are 14.9 / 15.2 kcal / mol for **TS4b1** / **TS4b2**, respectively. Finally, aromatization by elimination of H in **IN4b** leads to indole **II** through **TS5b** ($\Delta G = 8.9$ kcal / mol from **IN4b**).

In addition, it is noteworthy that in acidic conditions the energy of the whole process is clearly inferior (around 15 kcal / mol). This is in agreement with experimental observations. Although the calculated energy barriers are too high, the inclusion of an

additional molecule in the vicinity of the water molecule that acts as a catalyst lowers these barriers (see Figures S18-S19 in the SI).

1,2-Cyclohexanediol and 1,3-propanediol

In order to expand the methodology, 1,2-cyclohexanediol was employed for the preparation of tetrahydrocarbazoles. Tetrahydrocarbazoles are relevant compounds in medicinal chemistry; however, their preparation requires hydrazine derivatives. Fisher indole synthesis is the easiest access to these structures. Looking in detail in the literature, Watanabe also reported on this transformation with moderated yields.¹² Madsen also corroborated this approach.¹⁰ Importantly, 1,2-cyclohexanediol has been employed for the preparation of piperazines.¹⁵ In figure 6 is presented the aniline scope with this diol. Two equivalents of diol were employed under identical conditions as employed for 2,3-butnediol. Trimethoxy derivative **7a** was prepared in excellent yield (99%). The corresponding compounds **7b-f** were obtained in moderates yields (from 33% to 45%). Tetracyclic compound **7g** was obtained in good yield (67%). When 1,2-diamino benzene (**1i**) was used a reagent, the corresponding quinoxaline **8** was isolated in 23%. Compound **8** and also compound **4** (2,3-dimethylquinoxaline from Figure 2) are a clear

evidence of the presence of amino ketones (Scheme 3). In the literature there are many examples of this reaction with 1,2-diols and **1,2-diaminobenzene (1i)**¹⁶⁻²⁰

Figure 6. Aniline scope with 1,2-cyclohexanediol.

Additional reactions were performed with asymmetric 1,2-propanediol. Under these conditions compounds **9a** and **9b** were obtained as a mixture under good yield (79%, scheme 3: bottom). **An 84/16 ratio** for the 2-methyl indole **9a** and the 3-methyl indole **9b** was observed. The presence of both isomers can be explained either by initial oxidation of different alcohols or the internal tautomeric equilibrium.²¹

Scheme 3. Mechanism rational for quinoxaline **8** formation and 1,2-propanediol reaction.

a) yield given for the isomeric mixture.

Finally, 1,3-propanediol was employed. Watanabe reported an original access towards

quinolines with homogeneous Ru(II) catalyst employing 1,3-propanediol and anilines.²²

Madsen combined a ruthenium catalyst with a Lewis acid also for such approach.²³ In our

previous studies with Pd/C and ZnO (Water/diol excess) a combination of λ -amino

alcohols and quinolines was observed with low yields.²⁴

In Figure 7 are presented the results of this reaction. As it can be seen, a combination of products was always obtained. Indeed, quinolines were the major products (compounds

10a, **11a** and quinoline) obtained in moderated yields (38%, 62% and 18 % respectively). Tetrahydroquinolines **10b**, **11b** and tetrahydroquinoline appeared as trace products. Interestingly, Julolidines were also isolated (compounds **10c**, **11c** and **12c**) in low yields. Bruenau reported on the synthesis of these compounds under similar conditions with and Iridium/BINAP catalyst.^[25] These results clearly indicate that more complex structures can be obtained with **distant alcohols**, and although selectivity is a major issue, even tricyclic compounds as natural and interesting products like Julolidines, can be synthesized.

Figure 7. Aniline scope with 1,3-propanediol.

Conclusion

Herein, 2,3-Dimethylindoles and tetrahydrocarbazoles synthesis are reported employing anilines and 1,2-diols under 1:2 molar ratio. Pt/Al₂O₃, ZnO and *p*-TSA catalyze this transformation using NMP as solvent (0.8 M). DFT calculations and mechanism studies have unveiled the relevance of *p*-TSA; indeed, a carbocation has been found as key intermediate in the mechanism. In addition, employing 1,3-propanediol as reagent, quinolines and Julolidines have been prepared.

Experimental Section

Computational methods. All calculations were carried out with the Gaussian 09 suite of programs.²⁶ Initially, density functional theory²⁷ calculations (DFT) have carried out using the B3LYP²⁸ exchange-correlation functionals, together with the standard 6-31G(d) basis set, in gas phase.²⁹ The stationary points were characterized by frequency computations in order to verify that TSs have one and only one imaginary frequency. The intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) paths³⁰ were traced in order to check the energy profiles connecting each TS to the two associated minima of the proposed mechanisms using the second order González–Schlegel integration method.³¹ Subsequently, the inclusion of solvent effects have been considered by using a relatively simple self-consistent reaction

field (SCRF) method³² based on the polarizable continuum model (PCM) of Tomasi's group.³³ As solvents we have used N,N-dimethylacetamide (similar to 1-methylpyrrolidin-2-one used experimentally). The values of enthalpies, entropies and free energies in N,N-dimethylacetamide were calculated with the standard statistical thermodynamics at 423.15K.²⁹ Due to the presence of hydrogen bonds, and in order to obtain more precise energy results, all species have been recalculated by single-point energy calculation at the B3LYP-D3 level.

General Procedure. Aniline (1 equiv, 2 mmol) (THQ or indoline), 1.7% of Pt/Al₂O₃ (132.5 mg), 4.5% of ZnO nanoparticles (21.5 μ L) (<100 nm particle size (DLS), < 0 nm average particle size (APS), 20 wt % in H₂O), 5% of *p*-TSA H₂O (19 mg), diol (2 equiv, 4 mmol), and 2.5 mL of NMP were mixed manually inside a 50 mL quick-thread glass reaction tube. The tube was sealed with an Easy-On PTFE cap and put into a Carousel 12 Plus reaction station at 175 °C for 24-48 h (controlled by TLC). The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, and it needed to be opened carefully to depressurize the tube. After that, 15 mL of ethyl acetate was added, and the crude was filtered through a 0.45 μ m PTFE filter. The reaction mixture was washed with distilled water (3 \times 10 mL), and the organic layer was dried with Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated to afford the reaction

crude that was checked by ^1H NMR. The crude reaction product was purified by column chromatography using Merck 60 (0.040–0.063 mm) silica gel and a mixture of hexane (5) / ethyl acetate (1) as eluent.

Conflict of interest

The authors state that there are no conflicts to declare.

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